

Boltzmann versus Kaniadakis Entropy for Fermi-Dirac and Bose Einstein Cases

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In an earlier note (1), it was argued one may derive the Fermi-Dirac (FD), Bose-Einstein (BE) (and Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB)) distributions using only time reversal balanced elastic reactions. For example, given $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((1a)) one may find dynamical factors needed for such a reaction. For the FD case, one may use $f(e_1)(1-f(e_3))f(e_2)(1-f(e_4)) = f(e_2)(1-f(e_1))f(e_4)(1-f(e_3))$ ((1b)). Taking the \ln of ((1b)) and equating to energy conservation yields the FD distribution. A similar approach applies to the MB and BE cases. Thus, no information about phase space and no concept of entropy is needed. Following Kaniadakis (2), one may formally write a kinematical function k such that $\ln(k(f(e_1))) + \ln(k(f(e_2))) = \ln(k(f(e_3))) + \ln(k(f(e_4)))$ ((2)). Thus: $\ln(k)$ is the inverse of $f(e)$. Kaniadakis integrates $\ln(k(f(e)))$ over df to obtain an entropy density which may be coupled with the Lagrange multiplier b $f(e) e$ (i.e. an overall fixed energy). The integral and derivative d/df are inverse functions so maximization leads to: $\ln(k(f(e))) = -be$ ((3)) which follows immediately from a time reversal balance approach i.e. ((1a)) and ((1b)) with no entropy needed.

The focus of this note, however, is to compare Kaniadakis entropy, which is directly linked to kinematics but not to phase space, with the Boltzmann entropy approach where entropy $S = -k \ln(\text{Number of States})$. In (3), the number of states is computed using various factorials which seem to incorporate phase space. These approaches of course yield the MB, FD and BE distributions, but only after one applies Stirling's approximation. It may, however, be unnecessary to think in terms of Stirling's approximation. For example, in information theory, one maximizes a macrostate probability $P_a = \text{Product over } i \text{ } f_i^{n_i}$ where $n_i = N f_i$, f_i being a probability for i , subject to the Lagrange constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f_i$. This yields the MB distribution, but no factorials appear. Instead, the usual Stirling's result follows from $\ln(f_i^{n_i})$. Thus, it is argued one might interpret the Stirling form of the Boltzmann entropy, which is very similar to the Kaniadakis entropy, in such a manner instead of in terms of counting states. The reason that counting states seems a little strange, at least for the BE case, is that there should be an enhancement in the probability P_n for a state with n bosons (4). This physical enhancement is plainly visible in the time reversal balance approach ((1a)) ((1b)), but does not seem to be clearly present for a counting scheme which gives each "arrangement" an equal weight of 1.

Time-Reversal Balance

As argued above, it seems one may obtain the MB, FD and BE distributions by determining the kinematical probability related to a time reversal balance of an elastic two body collision $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. For the MB case, one may argue the probability for e_1 and e_2 to react is $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ which must balance $f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Taking \ln of both sides and equating $\ln(f(e_i)) = -1/T (e_i - u)$ where u is the chemical potential yields the MB distribution. Note: $\exp(-u/T)$ is the normalization constant for $N=1$.

For the FD case, things are not as simple as e_1 cannot change to e_3 if the state e_3 is occupied. On average, if there is a probability $f(e_3)$ that state 3 is occupied, then $1-f(e_3)$ is used

as an average hinderance factor so $f(e_1)$ is replaced with $f(e_1)(1-f(e_3))$ (and similar results for $f(e_2)$ on the LHS and, $f(e_3)$ and $f(e_4)$ on the RHS) and one is led to: $\ln[f(e_1) / (1-f(e_1))] = -1/T (e_1-u)$.

For the BE case, there is an enhancement instead of a hinderance factor, namely $1+f(e_3)$ so $f(e_1)$ is replaced with $f(e_1)/(1+f(e_1))$ and similar results for $f(e_2)$, $f(e_3)$ and $f(e_4)$. The same procedure then leads to the BE result.

This approach requires no knowledge of the phase space details, no counting of states and no knowledge of entropy. Furthermore, it seems to be directly linked to the physics in the problem i.e. the enhancement or hindrance of a reaction.

Boltzmann Entropy

Boltzmann entropy may be given by $S = -k \ln(\text{Number of States})$. Here we set $k=1$. Thus, it seems one needs to find the number of states. (It should also be noted that in the H theorem, $f_i \ln(f_i)$ appears and furthermore in the Boltzmann transport equation one has $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ as an equilibrium solution which matches the kinematical approach.)

Thus, one does not really need to find the number of states, calculate S and then vary it subject to the constraint $\sum_i f_i e_i = E_{ave}$. Nevertheless, we consider the approach outlined in (3) for which the number of states is calculated for the MB, FD and BE cases. In all cases, one assumes identical particles.

We argue it seems confusing that different expressions are used for the MB and BE cases. If one argues as in (4) that the probability to have a boson scatter into a state with n bosons is enhanced by $n+1$, there is a physical difference between the MB and BE cases. In the MB case, there is no such enhancement. If one is counting states, however, with each arrangement carrying a weight of 1, it is not clear why the MB and BE cases are different. Furthermore, it is not clear why the state counting approach depends critically on phase space.

In (2), it is argued that each energy level e_i is broken into g_i cells. These cells become phase space in later calculations, but are first thought of as identical cells representing the same energy. Then, it is argued one has n_i particles for each level e_i . For the MB case, the first particle may be placed in any of the g_i boxes. The same argument applies to all n_i particles so:

$$\text{Number of states} = \frac{g_i^{n_i}}{n_i!} \quad ((4))$$

One divides by $n_i!$ because the particles are identical. It seems that ((4)) is unusual. In general, n_i is taken to be very large so Stirling's approximation may be used and g_i is considered to be large as well. Consider, however, $g_i=2$ and $n_i=2$. Then, the number of states is 2 from ((4)), but that cannot be because one may have two particles in $g_i=1$, two particles in $g_i=2$ and one each in $g_i=1$ and $g_i=2$. This problem does not disappear as one increases n_i or g_i .

For the BE case, one considers g_i cells or g_i-1 partitions. (For example, two cells would have one wall between them.) Imagine there are two fixed outer walls. Then one permutes n_i+g_i-1

and divides by $n_i!$ and $(g_i-1)!$ because the particles are identical as are the walls. The permutation is $(n_i+g_i-1)!$. Thus:

The Number of states for the BE case is $= \frac{(n_i+g_i-1)!}{[n_i!](g_i-1)!}$ ((5))

The question asked in this note is why does not ((5)) apply to both the BE and the MB cases? What is the difference between the two if one is only counting states with each arrangement carrying a weight of 1?

The general idea is to take $-\ln$ of ((5)), use Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ and extremize subject to $\sum n_i = N$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier. ((4)) then yields the MB distribution multiplied by g_i and ((5)) the BE distribution multiplied by g_i .

As an example, consider ((5))

$(n_i+g_i-1) \ln(n_i+g_i-1) - n_i \ln(n_i) - b n_i$ is to be extremized in a straightforward manner leading to the BE distribution.

For the FD case, the counting of states is perhaps more reasonable as one uses:

Number of states $= \frac{g_i!}{(n_i!)(g_i-n_i)!}$

The point to be made is that in all of these counting approaches, Stirling's approximation:

$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n$ approx $= n \ln(n)$ ((6))

is used. It may be noted, however, that $n \ln(n)$ need not originate from the \ln of $n!$. For example:

$\ln(n^n) = n \ln(n)$ and might have a completely different interpretation than that of counting.

Kaniadakis Entropy

In (2), a kinematical approach is taken, very similar to the time reversal approach of ((1a)) and ((1b)), but an entropy density is explicitly calculated. First one finds from kinematics:

$\ln(k(f(e))) = -(e-u)/T$ ((7))

Next, one integrates $\ln(k(f))$ over df . Taking the derivative later returns $\ln(k(f))$ which is then set equal to the derivative of $d/df -1/T (e_i-u) f_i$ which is identical to stating ((7)).

For the BE case one has:

$$S \text{ density} = - \int df \ln(f/(1+f)) = - \int df [\ln(f) - \ln(1+f)]$$

Integrating by parts yields:

$$S \text{ density} = f \ln(f) - (1+f) \ln(1+f) \quad ((8)) \text{ for BE}$$

A very similar result holds for the FD case.

$$S \text{ density} = f \ln(f) - (1-f) \ln(1-f) \quad ((9)) \text{ for BE}$$

This is of the same form as the extremization of the Boltzmann entropy except for the fact that there is no g_i and no counting is used. Thus, one may ask whether a different interpretation may apply. For the MB case, one may use:

$$S \text{ density} = - \int df \ln(f) = - f \ln(f) \quad ((10)), \text{ but this is Shannon's entropy density.}$$

The Shannon entropy approach does not make use of counting, rather it uses probabilities. For example, consider the probability for a macrostate as:

$$P_a = \prod_i f_i^{N_i} \quad ((11))$$

$$P_a = \exp \left(\sum_i f_i \ln(f_i) \right) \quad ((12))$$

Thus, one could maximize Shannon's entropy subject to an energy constraint $\sum_i e_i f_i = E_{ave}$.

In this note, we argue that ((8)) and ((9)) might have similar interpretations. For the FD case, one does not simply have states that are occupied, but also holes. Thus, overall entropy might be based on a scheme considering both. In more general terms, one might see f_i as a probability and $1/(1-f_i)$ as hindrance. Thus ((9)) might be interpreted in terms of:

$$P(\text{FD}) = \text{Probability for macrostate} * \text{Probability of hindrance} \quad ((13)) \text{ where}$$

$$\ln(\text{Probability for macrostate}) = -f \ln(f) \quad \text{and} \quad \ln(\text{Probability of hindrance}) = + (1-f)\ln(1-f)$$

For the BE case, one has similar results, namely:

$$\ln(\text{Probability for macrostate}) = -f \ln(f) \quad \text{and} \quad \ln(\text{Probability of hindrance}) = + (1+f)\ln(1+f)$$

In such a case, one would not need a counting scheme at all, and entropy would be linked to macrostate probabilities which in turn would be linked to physical hindrances or enhancements. Simply using the time reversal approach of ((1a)) ((1b)), however, would bypass entropy altogether.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the counting scheme in (3), used for counting MB and BE states yields two different results, while there seems to be no physical reason for the two to be different if one assigns equal weights to all arrangements. In other words, it does not seem that MB and BE states are being physically distinguished in the counting scheme. Rather, an approximate counting scheme is used for the MB case, and an accurate one for the BE one. Furthermore, Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ seems to be key to the results and the form $n \ln(n)$ may be obtained in other ways which may have completely different interpretations. We argue one may find equilibrium distributions by time reversal balances of elastic collisions following ((1a) and ((1b)). If one wishes to express these in terms of entropy, one may use the Kaniadakis approach (2) where one begins with the time reversal balance result:

$\ln(k(f(e))) = -1/T (e-u)$ where k is kinematical function and integrates it over df .

This expression may then be differentiated with respect to f subject to $b f_i e_i$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier. This yields a result of the same mathematical form as the counting result, but without any phase space present. Furthermore, there is no assumption of counting as the result is of Shannon's entropy form, but with two terms for the BE and FD cases i.e.

BE case $-f \ln(f) + (1+f) \ln(1+f)$

These may be thought of as coming from the following:

Probability = Probability of a macrostate Probability of enhancement

Or $\ln(\text{Probability}) = -f \ln(f) + (1+f) \ln(1+f)$

The first term is the regular Shannon's entropy, but the BE and FD cases alter this.

References

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